

School Management: Proposition of a Management Model

Alequexandre Galvez de Andrade, Nélio Fernando dos Reis & Emiliano Estigarribia Canese

Abstract

The aim of this study was to develop a model for management education in public schools. The education comprises several actors and aspects that involve political processes, operational and teaching. There is a tendency to treat the school management in public schools only from a political point of view and pedagogical, reducing the importance of the management procedures, which impairs the school autonomy and reduces the empowerment of the environment as a space the construction of competences to exercise full citizenship. To outline the procedures, the first step was to use a bibliometric research, measuring the network of relationships between authors, year of publication of articles and density, in the second moment was performed a content analysis and confirmatory factorial to identify the relationship of words in the group and between the groups, finally it was proposed a model for school management. Due to these characteristics, this study is a theoretical essay. As a conclusion, the model of the wheel of school management, has 17 items to be observed in the management. This study can be applied in school management, primarily the public.

Keywords: School Management, Participatory Management, Autonomy, Multicultural Society, Democracy.

IJSB

Accepted 18 August 2019
Published 23 August 2019
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3375383

About Author

Alequexandre galvez de Andrade (corresponding author), Students of the Doctoral Program of the Universidad Columbia del Paraguay, Lecture at the Instituto Federal de São Paulo, Department of Administration.

Nélio Fernando dos Reis, Lecture at the Instituto Federal de São Paulo, Department of Administration.

Emiliano Estigarribia Canese, Lecturer of the doctoral program in Business Administration from the Universidad Columbia del Paraguay.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education as a social process, budget unit and place of acquisition of knowledge, skills and attitudes shows all its complexity that should be present in the planning, organization, leadership and control of school organizations. The understanding of these agents and aspects, allow greater insight into the construction of knowledge, converging to an improvement of the school unit, which is in accordance with the constitutional provisions established in Brazil. Education as a social and political process of people allows a minimum of reflection that cannot be acquired under conditions which normally is offered (Freire, 1967, p. 70). In this context arise various arguments based on social and material evidences of the world, such as environment, multiculturalism, social inequality. This complex space and stimulus to a critical conscience defies the management of these institutions. What if you have as evidence of this domain can be punctuated by the deepening of social inequalities, highlighted by the Gini index, which measures the degree of concentration of income with scale between 0 and 1, being much closer to 1 best, note that Brazil occupies the position of 120^o in a total of 127 countries, i.e., a high concentration of income, perpetuated by public policies without equity, although it has improved with the social programs. According to studies by the Institute in 2013, for every R\$ 1.00 transferred, represents an increase of R\$ 1.78 in the Brazilian GDP (Castro, Ferreira, Fields, & Ribeiro, 2010). Many times, this management is conceived only from the point of view of pedagogical and political, reducing the importance of the management of administrative processes, people management, participation. This tripod is essential for the development of the school environment. To deepen these interactions, in the first moment was carried out a bibliometric analysis, considering the relationship between the authors, publications per year, and density. After this we selected the main clusters of networks. On these clusters was performed an analysis of content. To make it possible to study the relationship of words within the clusters and among them, was conducted a confirmatory factor analysis. The sequence was studied the analysis of similarity between the words to identify the influence of factors to be considered and evaluated in the school unit. Finally, it was created the figure called wheel of school management, which has 17 items that can be classified from 0 to 10 by the school community, being 0 non-existent and the closer to the 10 best.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Constitution of the Republic of Brazil 1988 (Brasil, 1988) In its Article 5 guarantees the right to life, liberty, security, and the property. Will that education systems are pedagogically standalone or if establishes a set of rules to classify students between prepared or unprepared, institutions, good or bad, students with success or failures, rich and poor? The era of the binaries, which classifies individuals and institutions in mathematical systems of computational logic, without considering the capacity of relationship, communication and other. In this conception is that we have a right to freedom?, or as indicated by Paulo Freire (1987) to deal with the banking education, we are a warehouse of expectations that want us to be, ready models, normal, highly delineated methodologically, who think in a rational logic and neoliberal, as puppet dolls entered in a selective Theater, where they are called endowed with those who have high storage capacity of content, disregarding the emotional intelligence, how would measure the emotional intelligence, ability to relationship?. According to the center for studies of Hannah Arendt (2007)

"The proposal that arises in the face of our individual and collective responsibility to the world in which we live is not a manual for the practical policy, for the educational practice, a doctrine,

a code of ethics, but the devaluation of the shallowness of what we say and the automatism of what we do and, with it, the valuation of thought and imagination to search for words and actions more deep-rooted, manufactured or preservers."

Second Bendassolli (2007), several studies have sought to discover what is happiness, some studies point to the index of happiness of the Brazilian as the 22th-best ranking in the world report of the happiness of 2017, which takes into account the GDP, social assistance, life expectancy, freedom of choice, generosity, perception of corruption and Dystopia (Globe, 2017). Still in Bendassolli (2007, p. 4) there is the highlight of the possibility of accommodation in relation to the labor market. We need to question what the working relationship and happiness, "Some people believe that both do not have any relation, but rather contradictory: happy is he who does not need to work". There is a paradox between the ideal of happiness, a good life and success. To analyze the GINI index, which measures the degree of concentration of income with scale between 0 and 1, being much closer to 1 best, note that Brazil occupies the position of 120^o in a total of 127 countries (Wolfenbüttel, 2004), i.e., a high concentration of income, perpetuated by public policies without equity, although it has improved with the social programs. According to studies by the Institute in 2013, for every R\$ 1.00 transferred, represents an increase of R\$ 1.78 in the Brazilian GDP (Castro, Ferreira, Campos, & Ribeiro, 2010). In this perspective of linking success to work, it is observed that certainly occur frustrations, giving the idea that unemployment is associated with disability. However, it is a tool of capital to control supply and demand, reducing wages and labor rights and even imposing the ideology that the problem lies in the failure of the person by non-specialization, schooling or even the dysfunction of the education system. Life can be seen from the biological point of view and from a social point of view. Let us discuss the racial question as a point of attention to social patterns created in the imagination of human perversity. According to Gomes (2003, p. 77), "Today is proven by biology and genetics that all humans have the same genetic load", any theory that we learned through the hegemony of ideas is deconstructed from this perspective, this means as the author that discrimination is the fruit of our imagination stimulated by means of culture. The problem is which has interests behind these curricula. It is important to note what Candau (2002), described on the processes of globalisation as standardization, i.e., there is preaching of monocultures. But we are faced with a multicultural society. It is notorious the invasion in the minds of crops aimed for domination to imagine the happiness in this model. This is not to change the world, but to understand it to exercise the freedom. As Banks (1993) points out, the path runs by the pedagogy of fairness, all cultures are important and there is no upper cultures, in addition to the importance of the empowerment of school culture, where there will be a greater involvement of students in everyday issues and planning, including the possibility of discussing the PPC course of full and democratic way. For Paulo Freire (1967, p. 70) "The dialogical implies in the social and political responsibility of man. Requires a minimum of transitive consciousness, which is not in accordance with the conditions offered by the great domain". In this perspective it is needed to extrapolate and offer activities for extension and research for more flexible than the traditional curriculum cannot reach. To deepen the debate on sustainability Carrol (1979), makes a hierarchy, indicating that the basis for good economic sustainability is a very close relationship with the management of organizations and their ability to generate positive results. In this pyramid starting from base to top, it presents the economic liability, legal responsibility, ethical responsibility and accountability philanthropic organizations. In this way organizations need to have resources, obey the laws, doing what is right, correct and fair and improve the quality of life of the

people. In this sense, mainly in public organizations, one of the ways to discourage the services offered to the population is systematically cut budgets, imposing schedules that reduce the maximum possible services and informing the population that services do not serve the public interest. In this context educational complex under strong tendency of budget reduction, efficient and effective management contributes to achieving organizational objectives under different perspectives.

3 METHODOLOGY

To understand this universe, we carried out a bibliometric analysis, contributing to understand the debate that is being built in the country or countries (Soares, Carneiro, Calmon, & Castro, 2016). was first performed an analysis on the platform "Science Direct" and "Spell" with the construct "Education in the title and in the key word, Management," appeared only three articles that had no relation with this work, we opted to choose the platform Google Scholar, filtering only articles in Portuguese, to understand the local reality. After this, the lifting of the quantity and relations between the articles. Figure 1 shows the main authors and the relationship between them.

Figure 1: Network of knowledge among the authors

Source: The Authors

After the analysis by author, were separated clusters, which represented at least 3 relationships, this procedure aims to identify and filter the most relevant work. Figure 2 present the Clusters. To identify the publication per year and understand the interest of science by theme, proceeded with the analysis of the articles by age, figure 3. As shown in Figure 3, from 2005 there is an interest in the Brazilian Academy on the theme, the years that appear with the highest number of searches are between 2005 to 2010 and from 2015 to 2019. Demonstrating that in the period from 2010 to 2014, there were comparatively few researches. Whereas the network, it should be noted that studies with greater relationship are in the range of 2015 to 2019. This intend that the academy has recently given prominence to the theme. Based on the assumptions of the authors' analysis, were separated 20 articles, according to Table 1, in order to understand and deepen the content discussed. These articles were selected the abstract, which deals with all aspects of the work. Thus, for the treatment of data was used the content analysis technique, which has as its objective the fragmentation of texts to find regularities, considering the frequency, allowing comparisons (Nascimento & Menandro, 2006).

Figure 2: Clusters with relationships

Source: The authors

Figure 3: Publication of articles per year

Source: The authors

Table 1: Articles object of study

(BARROSO, 2009)	(Souza, 2012)	(NETO & CASTRO, 2011)
(VIEIRA, 2011)	(Abrucio, 2010)	(Alonso, 2004)
(VIEIRA, 2011)	(Alonso, 2004)	(Brandão & Silva, 2009)
(LUCK, 2002)	(Gracindo, 2012)	(Souza, 2012)
(Russo, 2008)	(Silva, 2001)	(Este & Mineiro, 2002)
(Machado, 2012)	(FONSECA & OLIVEIRA, 2011)	(Dourado, 2007)
(Aguiar, 2008)	(Prata, 2002)	

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The corpus was constituted by nine texts, separated into 157 segments of Text (ST), with utilization of 100 (63.69%). Emerged 5,506 occurrences (words, shapes or words), being 1,197 and 4,309 distinct words with a single occurrence. The content analyzed was categorized into 3 categories: Class 1, with 34 ST (34% of the total); Class 2, with 29 (29%); Class 3 with 37 (37% of the total). For the purpose of this study is considered statistically relevant classes that have $x^2 > 3.84$ and index of significance $p < 0.05$. The class 1 comprises 34 ST that represent 34% of the total. Consisting of words and radicals in the interval between with $x^2 = 3.04$ (field) and 23.81 (research). Were eliminated from the analysis the words field, Brazil, greater achievement, Subject, country, by not expressing 95% confidence intervals. Table 2 shows the data related to the Right

Table 2: Cluster 1

n...	eff. s.t.	eff. total	pourcentage	chi2	type	forme	P
1	7	8	87.5	11.09	nom	desempenho	0.00086
2	5	5	100.0	10.22	nom	lugar	0.00139
3	5	5	100.0	10.22	adj	acadêmico	0.00139
4	5	5	100.0	10.22	adj	obtido	0.00139
5	5	5	100.0	10.22	nom	motivação	0.00139
6	5	5	100.0	10.22	nom	base	0.00139
7	6	7	85.71	8.97	nom	caso	0.00274
8	6	7	85.71	8.97	nom	dimensão	0.00274
9	10	15	66.67	8.39	nom	estudo	0.00376
10	4	4	100.0	8.09	adj	metodológico	0.00445
11	4	4	100.0	8.09	adj	seguinte	0.00445
12	10	16	62.5	6.89	nom	resultado	0.00864
28	6	8	75.0	6.51	adj_num	dois	0.01070
13	3	3	100.0	6.0	nom	problema	0.01427
14	3	3	100.0	6.0	nom	dado	0.01427
15	3	3	100.0	6.0	adj	paulista	0.01427
16	3	3	100.0	6.0	nom	lado	0.01427
17	3	3	100.0	6.0	nom	conclusão	0.01427
29	3	3	100.0	6.0	adj_num	terceiro	0.01427
30	3	3	100.0	6.0	adj_num	dez	0.01427

Source: The authors

In Class 2 There are 29 ST which represents 29% of the total. Consisting of words and radicals in the interval between with $x^2 = 2.13$ (direction) and 18.43 (domination). Were eliminated from the analysis the words direction, quotidian, domineering, Weber and school, by presenting $x^2 < 3.84$ and significance $p > 0.05$. Table 3 presents the information from the Cluster 2. In Class 3 There are 37 ST that represent 37% of the total. Consisting of words and radicals in the interval between $x^2 = 2.23$ (political) and 26.32 (education). Were eliminated from the analysis political words, objective, element, mechanism, learning theory, and teaching, by presenting $x^2 < 3.84$ and significance $p > 0.05$. Table 4 presents the information from the Cluster 3. Analyzing the dendrogram, figure 4, obtained by the analysis of tables 1, 2 and 3, it is observed that the word education, pedagogical, management and democratic, are related with domination, government and politics. A little further away appear the words research, performance, place and academic. Through the analysis of similarity, the interconnection between the words can be more strong or weak (Chi-Square test), the words management, school and school represent greater strength and less strength are the words policy, domination and form, as shown in Figure 5. On the shaft Management, appear the words democracy, political process, quality, studies. Already on shaft school, feature-if the words performance, audience, result, evaluation and finally on Axis 3 the words related to education are compared, workplace and community. Transforming these three axes so that the school unit can make an analysis of the current planning, built up the wheel of school management, as shown in figure 6.

Table 3: Cluster 2

n...	eff. s.t.	eff. total	pourcentage	chi2	Type	forme	P
0	7	7	100.0	18.43	nom	dominação	< 0,0001
1	6	6	100.0	15.63	nom	governo	< 0,0001
2	11	16	68.75	14.62	nom	política	0.00013
3	7	8	87.5	14.45	nom	função	0.00014
4	5	5	100.0	12.89	nom	dirigente	0.00033
5	7	9	77.78	11.43	nom	forma	0.00072
6	4	4	100.0	10.2	nom	domínio	0.00140
7	4	4	100.0	10.2	nom	condução	0.00140
8	7	10	70.0	9.07	nom	relação	0.00259
9	3	3	100.0	7.57	nom	mundo	0.00592
10	3	3	100.0	7.57	nom	disputa	0.00592
11	3	3	100.0	7.57	adj	forte	0.00592
12	4	5	80.0	6.65	nom	administração	0.00992
13	4	5	80.0	6.65	nom	pessoa	0.00992
14	3	4	75.0	4.28	nom	papel	0.03851
15	17	47	36.17	2.21	nom	escola	NS (0.13674)
16	2	3	66.67	2.13	nom	weber	NS (0.14433)
17	2	3	66.67	2.13	adj	dominador	NS (0.14433)
18	2	3	66.67	2.13	adj	cotidiano	NS (0.14433)
19	2	3	66.67	2.13	nom	direção	NS (0.14433)

Source: The authors

Table 4: Cluster 3

n...	eff. s.t.	eff. total	pourcentage	chi2	Type	forme	P
0	15	16	93.75	26.32	nom	educação	< 0,0001
1	10	10	100.0	18.92	adj	pedagógico	< 0,0001
2	26	45	57.78	15.15	nom	gestão	< 0,0001
3	12	15	80.0	14.0	adj	democrático	0.00018
4	7	7	100.0	12.82	nom	projeto	0.00034
5	7	8	87.5	9.51	nom	comunidade	0.00203
6	5	5	100.0	8.96	nom	avaliação	0.00275
7	5	5	100.0	8.96	nom	concepção	0.00275
8	9	12	75.0	8.45	nom	ação	0.00365
9	6	7	85.71	7.66	adj	básico	0.00563
10	22	42	52.38	7.35	adj	escolar	0.00670
11	4	4	100.0	7.09	adj	participativo	0.00773
12	4	4	100.0	7.09	nom	conselho	0.00773
13	4	4	100.0	7.09	nom	autor	0.00773
14	9	13	69.23	6.66	nom	trabalho	0.00986
15	5	6	83.33	5.88	nom	qualidade	0.01532
16	5	6	83.33	5.88	nom	programa	0.01532
17	5	6	83.33	5.88	nom	participação	0.01532
18	3	3	100.0	5.27	nom	autonomia	0.02174
19	3	3	100.0	5.27	nom	implementação	0.02174

Source: The authors

Figure 4: Dendrogram

Source: The authors

Figure 5: Analysis of similarity

Source: The authors

In Figure 6, for each item should be assigned a note of 0 to 10, being 0 totally insufficient and much closer to 10 best. If there is more than one participant to obtain general note per item, it is suggested to use the average or fashion. Example: For the item Transparency, participated 5 teachers who attributed the notes, 5,4,7,7,8. If the total was calculated by averaging, this item would note equal to 6.2, it has already been used to fashion, the note would be 7. It is recommended that the activities must be participative with the involvement of the students through their representatives or committees, especially in processes related to school space. This construction is needed to strengthen the culture, identity and autonomy. In possession of these maps, you must build the action plans with the school community, the results of the initiatives should be monitored so that they can monitor the efficiency of the processes. This cycle must be repeated periodically, as established by the school unit.

Figure 6: Wheel of School Management

Source: The authors

3. Conclusion

The objective of this study was to develop a model for school management in public schools that will allow the improvement of planning and control. It was developed the wheel of school management with 17 items. This tool allows managers to identify the points to be improved and refined, by means of a note for each item that varies from 0 to 10, being 0 non-

existent and the closer to the 10 best. In addition, you can also be used for the control of actions in progress or completed. It is recommended to be completed by the school community. In the case of students, you can form committees. To obtain the note when completed by more than one participant, it is suggested to use the average or fashion. The discussion about the items of the wheel of School Management can be performed in the pedagogical meetings, which become more systematized and discuss broader issues that the training requirements.

References

- Abrucio, F. L. (2010). Gestão escolar e qualidade da educação: um estudo sobre dez escolas paulistas Fernando. *XV Congreso Internacional Del CLAD Sobre La Reforma Del Estado y de La Administración Pública*, (2006), 1-21.
- Aguiar, M. A. da S. (2008). Gestão da educação básica e o fortalecimento dos Conselhos Escolares. *Educar Em Revista*, (31), 129-144. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s0104-40602008000100009>
- Alonso, M. (2004). Gestão escolar: revendo conceitos. *São Paulo: PUC-SP*, 1-9. Retrieved from http://cursoonlineinformaticaprofessores.pbworks.com/w/file/attach/54022785/gestao_revendoconceitos.pdf
- BARROSO, J. (2009). A UTILIZAÇÃO DO CONHECIMENTO EM POLÍTICA: O CASO DA GESTÃO ESCOLAR EM PORTUGAL. *Educação & Sociedade ISSN:*, 30(109), 987-1007.
- Brandão, A., & Silva, M. J. (2009). Campo minado. *Metalurgia e Materiais*, 65(597), 82-83.
- Brasil. (1988). Constituição da República Federativa do Brasil. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13398-014-0173-7.2>
- Castro, J. A. de, Ferreira, H. R. S., Campos, A. G., & Ribeiro, J. A. C. (2010). Perspectivas da política social no Brasil (p. 452). Instituto de Pesquisa Econômica Aplicada. Retrieved from http://ipea.gov.br/agencia/images/stories/PDFs/livros/livros/Livro_perspectivasdapolitica.pdf
- Dourado, L. F. (2007). Políticas e gestão da educação básica no Brasil: limites e perspectivas. *Educação & Sociedade*, 28(100), 921-946. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s0101-73302007000300014>
- Este, R., & Mineiro, S. (2002). EFEITO DO PERFIL DO DIRETOR A GESTÃO ESCOLAR SOBRE A PROFICIÊNCIA DO ALUNO. *ESTUDOS EM AVALIAÇÃO EDUCACIONAL*, 17(34), 155-186.
- FONSECA, M., & OLIVEIRA, J. F. DE. (2011). A gestão escolar no contexto das recentes reformas educacionais brasileiras. *Revista Brasileira de Política e Administração Da Educação*, 25(2), 233-246. <https://doi.org/10.21573/vol25n22009.19493>
- Gracindo, R. (2012). O gestor escolar e as demandas da gestão democrática: exigências, práticas, perfil e formação. *Retratos Da Escola*, 135-147. Retrieved from <http://www.esforce.org.br/index.php/semestral/article/view/107>
- LUCK, H. (2002). *A DIMENSÃO PARTICIPATIVA DA GESTÃO ESCOLAR*.
- Machado, C. (2012). Avaliação Externa e Gestão Escolar: Reflexões sobre usos dos resultados. *Revista @mbienteeducação*, 5(1), 70-82.
- Nascimento, A. R. A. do, & Menandro, P. R. M. M. (2006). Estudos e Pesquisas em Psicologia Análise lexical e análise de conteúdo : uma proposta de utilização conjugada Lexical analysis and content analysis : a proposal for conjugate utilization. *Estudos E Pesquisas Em Psicologia*, (2004), 72-88.
- NETO, A. C., & CASTRO, A. M. D. A. (2011). GESTÃO ESCOLAR EM INSTITUIÇÕES DE ENSINO MÉDIO: ENTRE A GESTÃO DEMOCRÁTICA E A GERENCIAL. *Educação & Sociedade ISSN:*
- Prata, C. L. (2002). Gestão Escolar E As Tecnologias. *Formação de Gestores Escolares Para Utilização de Tecnologias de Informação e Comunicação*.
- Russo, M. H. (2008). Escola e paradigmas de gestão. *EccoS - Revista Científica*, 6(1), 25-42. <https://doi.org/10.5585/eccos.v6i1.366>
- Silva, J. J. C. (2001). Gestão escolar participada e clima organizacional. *Gestão Em Ação*, 4(2), 49-60.
- Soares, P. B., Carneiro, T. C. J., Calmon, J. L., & Castro, L. O. da C. de O. (2016). Análise bibliométrica da produção científica brasileira sobre Tecnologia de Construção e Edificações na base de dados Web of Science TT - Bibliometric analysis of the Brazilian scientific production on Building and

- Construction Technologies in the Web of . *Ambiente Construído*, 16(1), 175–185.
<https://doi.org/10.1590/s1678-86212016000100067>
- Souza, Â. R. De. (2012). A natureza política da gestão escolar e as disputas pelo poder na escola. *Revista Brasileira de Educação*, 17(49), 159–174. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s1413-24782012000100009>
- VIEIRA, S. Lerc. (2011). Políticas e gestão da educação básica: revisitando conceitos simples. *Revista Brasileira de Política e Administração Da Educação*, 23(1), 53–69. <https://doi.org/10.21573/vol23n12007.19013>
- WOLFFENBÜTTEL, Andréa. What is the Gini index. IPEA, 2004. Access in: 04 nov 2014. Available in: <desafiosipea.gov.br>.

Cite this article:

Alequexandre galvez de Andrade, Nélio Fernando dos Reis & Emiliano Estigarríbia Canese (2019). School Management: Proposition of a Management Model. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 3(5), 99-108.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3375383>

Retrieved from <http://ijsab.com/wp-content/uploads/392.pdf>

Published by

